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Flavone glycosides from the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia*

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FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia* two flavone glycosides, (i) acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside and (ii) 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside and also an anthraquinone glycoside have been isolated and studied.

The first compound, m.p. 244°-45°, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{12}O_{10}$, when hydrolysed with mineral acid gave acacetin $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ and glucose. The structure of acacetin has been confirmed by analysis colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with 7-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shift using aluminium chloride¹ and sodium acetate². That glucose is present in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation and nature of the glycoside linkage as β - has been confirmed by its hydrolysis with emulsin.

The other flavone glycoside m.p. 178°-80° (d), molecular formula $C_{23}H_{24}O_{10}$, on hydrolysis with mineral acid gave an aglycone $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ (m.p. 295°) and galactose. The aglycone has been shown to be 5,7-dimethyl apigenin by analysis, colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with the 4'-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shifts using ethoxide reagent³. That galactose is in the pyranose form has been established by periodate oxidation and the β -linkage of the glycoside by hydrolysis with emulsin.

The compound acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside is known and has been reported earlier from several plant sources^{4,5}. The other glycoside, 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside, has not been reported earlier from any plant source, though another glycoside namely 5,7-dimethyl-4'-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside has been recently reported by Dubey and Mishra⁶ from sugar cane peelings.

The third compound isolated from this plant is an anthraquinone glycoside which is being studied and will be reported later.

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Mixed ligand complexes of Bis (ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with nitrogen donors

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β DIKETONES and related compounds which exhibit keto-enol tautomerism react with metal cations to form complexes which behave as Lewis acids and form adducts with Lewis bases. Several such base adducts of β -diketonates of Zn(II) and copper(II) have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. The complexes of β -keto esters closely resemble those of β -diketonates. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the base adduct formation with ethylacetoacetato complexes and this communication describes eight base adducts of bis(ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with quinoline and isoquinoline.

Experimental

Metal chelates were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with ethylacetoacetato in (1 : 2) ratio followed by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. Bis(ethylacetoacetato) metal(II) was suspended in minimum volume of ethanol and base was added in (1 : 2) ratio and the mixture refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. On keeping the clear solution overnight crystalline compounds separated out.

Metal and nitrogen in the compounds were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using "Toshniwal's Conductivity Bridge". Infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in *M*/100 (chloroform base mixture) solution with Hilger Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility

NOTES

measurements were made on solid specimens at 25° by Gouy method. Analytical data are recorded in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present investigation are of the composition $[ML_2B_2]$, where 'M' is Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II); LH-ethylacetoacetate and 'B', is quinoline or isoquinoline. Copper and nickel complexes are green and blue crystalline, cobalt complexes are pink crystalline and zinc complexes are white crystalline. All the compounds have low melting points, are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium the Λ_M values are very low being of the order of (5-15) mhos (Table 1) suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements show the copper(II) complexes to be paramagnetic with the presence of one unpaired electron, μ_{eff} values being of the order of (1.8-1.9) B.M. (Table 1). Magnetic moments of Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes are of the order of (3.1-3.2) and (4.9-5.0) B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of two and three unpaired electrons respectively as expected for a highspin octahedral configuration.

bases since most of the ligand absorption bands are shifted. $\nu(M-O)$, $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(C-O)$, $\nu(C-C)$ for base adducts of ethylacetoacetate are recorded in Table 2. Other bands of ethylacetoacetate are not recorded since there is considerable overlapping by the bonded nitrogen bases. Infrared spectra of β -keto esters have been previously reported⁶.

In general there will be considerable electron release resulting in shifting of M-O, C-O and C-C bands of chelate to higher frequency region when an additional ligand (nitrogen base) is bonded to the metal ion, but superimposed on this effect there will be π -bonding between the metal and heteroligand atom which results in electron drain from the ring system shifting the above bands to lower frequency region. So it is difficult to unambiguously predict whether these bands will shift to higher or lower frequency region. But definite and marked shifts in position of the bands indicate the bonding of the heteroligands to metal ions.

Electronic absorption spectra have been studied in the range of 180-1000 nm. Metal chelates have intense absorption bands in the U.V. around 265 nm which remains fairly constant for different metal complexes, from which it seems quite likely that

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour and form	M.P. (°C)	Conduc-tance (mhos)/cm ²	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% Metal		% Nitrogen	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	[Co L ₂ Q ₂]	Pink crystalline	117	8.5	4.95	9.88	10.25	4.54	4.87
2.	[Co L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂]	"	148	5.0	4.98	9.92	10.25	4.62	4.87
3.	[Ni L ₂ Q ₂]	Blue needles	133	10.0	3.12	10.35	10.21	4.68	4.87
4.	[Ni L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂]	"	178	11.4	3.18	9.86	10.21	4.59	4.87
5.	[Cu L ₂ Q ₂]	Green needles	200	6.8	1.84	10.68	10.96	4.66	4.84
6.	[Cu L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂]	"	215	8.4	1.86	10.71	10.96	4.60	4.84
7.	[Zn L ₂ Q ₂]	White crystalline	185	14.8	—	10.95	111.24	4.56	4.82
8.	[Zn L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂]	"	194	12.4	—	10.86	11.24	4.62	4.82

L = Anion of ethyl acetoacetate, Q = Quinoline, I.Q. = Isoquinoline.

TABLE 2. INFRARED SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) AND VISIBLE ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (nm) (ϵ)

Sl.No.	Compound	$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(C-C)$	$\nu(M-O)$	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu_{max} (\epsilon)$
1.	Co L ₂ Q ₂	1626	1525	480	285	500(35), 520(30)
2.	Co L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂	1625	1530	485	280	500(38), 525(35)
3.	Ni L ₂ Q ₂	1627	1530	465	250	390(65), 630(6.5), 940(3.8)
4.	Ni L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂	1627	1535	465	255	400(70), 620(6.8), 950(3.6)
5.	Cu L ₂ Q ₂	1600	1525	450	240	650(85)
6.	Cu L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂	1605	1525	455	240	675(120)
7.	Zn L ₂ Q ₂	1625	1520	422	235	—
8.	Zn L ₂ (I.Q.) ₂	1625	1525	420	235	—

Infrared spectra provide evidence for the formation of chelates as well as their adducts with nitrogen

this band is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the enolate ion rather than a charge transfer transition. Further,

the base adducts have absorption bands in the U.V. region around 220, 270 and 310 nm indicating E₁, E₂ (and the ester) and B bands respectively of the nitrogen base.

Copper complexes show one broad absorption band in the 650–675 nm region. It has been observed that greenish colours and absorptions in the vicinity of 700 nm are indicative of penta or hexa coordinated Cu(II). Recent studies⁹ on electronic spectra of Cu(II) indicate that the three transitions $2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_1$ (ν_1), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2B_2$ (ν_2), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2E$ (ν_3) are close in energy and often give rise to a single broad band envelope. So the present complexes probably have a distorted octahedral configuration. This is in conformity with some earlier observations by Graddon¹⁰ *et al.*

Cobalt(II) complexes have two absorption bands around 520 and 500 nm which may be assigned as the $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ transition. The splitting might be due to tetragonal distortion or spin-orbit coupling effect. Actually three spin allowed d-d transitions are expected for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. The $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$ transition which occurs around 1200 nm could not be recorded as it was beyond the range of instrument used. The other transition i.e., $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ is usually weak since it involves a two electron process. Weakness combined with closeness of this transition to $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$, renders it unobserved. The cobalt(II) complexes presumably have a highspin octahedral configuration as reported for adducts of Co(II) acetylacetonates by Fackler and co-workers¹¹ and Horrocks¹² *et al.*

Three absorption bands are noticed for nickel(II) complexes around 950, 630, 400 nm. Octahedral nickel(II) ion has three distinct spin-allowed transitions. The above three absorption bands may be assigned to the three transitions i.e., $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. Hence the nickel(II) complexes reported in the present investigation are highspin octahedral complexes similar to compounds reported earlier¹³. Complexes of zinc are six coordinated octahedral similar to the base adducts of acetylacetonates by Graddon¹⁴ *et al.*

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Synthesis of some Derivatives of Pyrazolo [3, 4-d]-pyrimidin-4, 6-diones*

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A number of quinazoline-4-ones and quinazoline-4,6-diones were earlier synthesised in our laboratories and some of them showed very interesting pharmacological properties. In continuation of our work in this field, some pyrazolo [3,4-d]-pyrimidin-4,6-diones were synthesised in order to find out what effect replacement of a benzo group by a pyrazolo group will have upon the pharmacological activity.

Ethyl ethoxymethylenecyanoacetate¹ was treated with phenylhydrazine to give 1-aryl-5-aminopyrazolo-4-carboxylate (I). Treatment of I with aryl or alkylisocyanate gave the urea derivative (II), which was cyclised with sodium ethoxide in ethanol to give the pyrazolo-[3,4-d]-pyrimidin-4,6-dione. Substituted phenylhydrazines were prepared by reported methods². The table gives the list of compounds which were prepared.

These compounds were screened for CNS depression properties and anti-inflammatory activity. None of the compounds showed any significant CNS depression properties. Quite a few of them showed anti-inflammatory properties. Compounds VIII and XII have shown anti-inflammatory properties equivalent to Aspirin in rats at 200 mg/kg dose level.

Experimental

1-phenyl-5-aminopyrazole-4-carboxylate (I) :

A mixture of ethyl ethoxymethylenecyanoacetate (16.9 g; 0.1 mole) and phenylhydrazine (10.8 g; 0.1 mole) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. Ethanol was distilled off under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture; m.p. 96–98° (reported³ 99–101°); yield = 15.6 g.

1-phenyl-5-phenylureidopyrazole-4-carboxylate (II) :

A mixture of I (4.6 g; 0.02 mole) and phenylisocyanate (2.4 g; 0.02 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml.) was

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